

SURFACE MODIFICATIONS ON BASALT FIBERS

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Abstract

Incompatibility between basalt fibers and phenolic resin matrices leads to poor interfacial bonding in their composites. This study aims to investigate the effects of plasma treatment on the basalt fiber surface properties. The scanning electron microscopy shows increased fiber surface roughness due to plasma treatment, which favors mechanical interlocking of the interface; The water contact angle test shows the plasma treatment technique do not wreck the wettability of basalt fibers. The result of the single fiber tensile strength indicates that the plasma treatments has no detectable influence on the basalt fiber tensile strength. Micro-bond test shows the changes of the interfacial shear strength of the basalt fibers. The interfacial shear strength (IFSS) are raised 41% when plasma treatment time are 30 and 40s, while 19% when plasma treatment time are 20s. Therefore, it can be concluded that the plasma treatments on the basalts can improve the basalt fibers' compatibility to the phenolic resin.

1. Introduction

Fiber-reinforced composite materials are part of the general class of engineering materials called composite materials. It is usual to divide all engineering materials into four class: metal, polymer, ceramics and composites. Because of the excellent property, such as high strength, high thermal

stability, naturally fire resistance, highly inert, and less harmful to human and the environment, etc. Basalt fiber-reinforced composites have been in service in engineering applications for many years. However, this fiber don't gain wide applications until fiber-reinforced polymer (FRP) composites are widely applied in modern industry. And now FRP composites continue to win widespread application in aerospace, automotive, and sports. And many researches have been carried out to develop environmental fiber materials for the last decade[3,4]. As a result, basalt fiber is found attractive as a new reinforcing fiber material. Basalt fiber is extruded from melted basalt rock that consists mainly of Si and Al oxides[5]. The tensile strength of single basalt fiber can be as high as 4800 MPa[4] and also it has excellent thermal and chemical stability. In addition, Basalt fiber has better mechanical properties than E-glass fiber, is more widely available and is cheaper than carbon fiber. Since its manufacturing process is simple (melting and extrusion) compared to that of glass fiber, basalt fiber consumes less energy, and reduces environmental waste such as carbon dioxide through the manufacturing process. With more and more product of basalt fiber reinforced polymer applying in civil engineering and other areas, there is an increasing need for the knowledge on the interface properties of basalt fiber reinforced polymer. It was well known that good adhesion was achieved through chemical bonding, favorable wettability and

mechanical interlocking, etc. Plasma technology has attracted much attention in surface modification of fibers for its environmentally favorable advantages. In recent years, atmospheric pressure plasma devices have been developed to overcome the drawbacks of low pressure plasma treatment in which an expensive and complicated vacuum system is required. It works under an open environment and has short treatment time, greater flexibility and fewer restrictions on the treated material.

Atmospheric-pressure non-thermal plasmas were produced by electrical discharges in the low gases. Most researches employed organic fibers, although surface modification of fibers by plasma treatment appeared to be a still very active field of technological researches. Previous works in this field focused on organic fibers. Comparatively very few researches have been conducted on inorganic fibers, especially basalt fibers. Some studies have investigated processes and mechanical and physical properties of basalt fiber and its composites with polymer matrices. M.T.Kim et al.[4] applied basalt fiber as a reinforcing material to epoxy resin, and the interfacial properties between basalt- fiber and epoxy resin are improved by oxygen plasma treatment, and this increased the interlaminar fracture toughness of basalt/epoxy woven composites. G.J.Wang et al.[7] also investigated the plasma-induced surface changes on morphologies and active group, the results exhibited a remarkable increase in chemical stability and excellent adhesion, accompanied by extensive etching.

However, the research about the surface modifications of basalt fiber is insufficient in particularly for a long term life, especially interface properties between basalt fibers and phenolic resin matrices, which have been applied widely in the high temperature resistant fields, like aviation and space, chemistry etc. Therefore, in this paper, the influence of the surface treatment such as the plasma treatments on the basalt fibers were investigated and analyzed. The effects of plasma treatments were discussed and clarified based on scanning electronic

microscope (SEM) observation, dynamic contact angle analysis, single fiber tensile strength test and the interfacial shear strength test of the fibers to the phenolic resin. And the basalt fibers were treated by an atmospheric pressure plasma jet system. The IFSS of fiber/matrix interface was measured by Micro-bond test.

2. Experimental

2.1 Materials

In this paper, the basalt fibers (diameter:13 micron; tensile strength: 2.5 GPa; modulus: 105 GPa) were provided by Shanxi Basalt Fiber Technology Co., Ltd.(Taiyuan,China). And the matrix was phenolic resin provided by SI Group-Shanghai Co.,Ltd.(Shanghai,China). Thermal properties of both basalt fiber and phenolic resin are superior. Both of them have outstanding stability to heat, retaining a high percentage of strength after exposure to temperatures to 600 °C for a limited time. It is proved that increasing of the time of tempering leads to the acceleration of structural changes[14].

2.2 Samples Preparation

The basalt fibers were randomly divided into two groups: untreated and plasma treated. The plasma

Fig.1. Diagram of APPJ system

treatment was carried out using an atmospheric pressure plasma jet (APPJ) system.

An APPJ system (Model Atomflo™-R 250 of Surfx Company,USA) was used for plasma treatment of the samples. The radio frequency was 13.56MHz and the discharge power was 40 W. Helium gas with a purity of 99.99% was introduced into a nozzle at a flow rate of 20 L/min and the plasma jet system covered an active area of 2mm×10 mm. The single basalt fibers were fixed on a frame with distance of 2 mm from the nozzle and were moved on a conveying belt vertical to the nozzle at a rate of 6 mm/s. The stationary treatment time was equivalent to 20, 30 and 40 s in choice. All the sample preparation and treatment were performed in an environment of 20 °C and 65% relative humidity(RH). Untreated group was used for the comparison of samples after plasma treated.

2.3 Micro-bond pull-out test

The samples preparation mainly involved manufacturing micro-droplets by tying a sphere of phenolic resin around a single basalt fiber. The samples were heated at 100 °C for 4 hours, then cooled down and balanced in an environment of 20°C and 65% RH. The process was carefully controlled in order to obtain a symmetrical droplet. The droplet size was also controlled to make it easy for testing but not to exceed the critical value that the fiber would fracture prior to Micro-bond pull-out test. A typical specimen is shown in Fig. 2. The embedded length, the beads width and the fiber diameter were measured using an LV100P polarized light microscope (model Nikon Ellipse) with a digital photographic system. The variability of basalt fiber cross-section must be considered when working at the micro-mechanics scale and it is assumed that drop length is small enough to be able to neglect fiber diameter variation within the droplet.

The Micro-bond pull-out test was conducted on

Fig.2 Polarized light microscope photograph of micro-bond specimen

Fig.3. Diagram of micro-bond pull-out test

an XQ-2 Fiber Tensile Testing Machine with a microwave. The diagram of the micro-bond pull-out test is shown in Fig. 3. The rate of the upper clamp displacement was 20 mm/min. The IFSS, τ_d , was calculated using the following equation derived from Shear-lag model:

$$\tau_d = \frac{F_d}{\pi d_f x} \quad (1)$$

Where F_d is the peak load, x is the embedded length, d_f is the radius of the fiber.

Fig.4. SEM photographs of different treatment time by plasma at high magnification and low magnification (B1 - 20s ; B2 - 30s ; B3 - 40s).

Table 1 Interfacial shear strength of control and treated samples with different plasma treatment times

Treatment	Sample size	IFSS (MPa)	
		Mean	Standard deviation
A - untreated	36	29.8	14.4
B1-plasma treated for 20s	38	35.5	12.2
B2-plasma treated for 30s	30	42.0	12.1
B3-plasma treated for 40s	34	42.1	11.3

Table 2 Tensile strength of control and treated basalt fibers with different plasma treatment times

Treatment	Sample size	Single fiber strength (GPa)	
		Mean	Standard deviation
A - untreated	22	2.50	2.0
B1-plasma treated for 20s	21	2.63	2.4
B2-plasma treated for 30s	24	2.47	3.7
B3-plasma treated for 40s	25	2.59	2.1

Table 3 Water contact angle of control and treated basalt fibers with different plasma treatment times

Treatment	Sample size	Contact angle(°)	
		Mean	Standard deviation
A - untreated	5	86	1.2
B1-plasma treated for 20s	5	81	3.2
B2-plasma treated for 30s	5	84	3.4
B3-plasma treated for 40s	5	80	5.1

Fig.5. Interfacial shear strength of untreated and treated samples

Fig.6. Tensile strength of untreated and treated samples

2.4 Single fiber tensile strength test

In order to determine if the treatment have adverse effect on the bulk property of the basalt fibers, single fiber tenacity was tested using an XQ-2 Fiber Tensile Testing Machine with a rate of upper clamp displacement of 20 mm/s and a gauge length of 20 mm under 20 °C and 65% RH condition. Fiber

diameters were measured by a LV100P polarized light microscope (model Nikon Ellipse) with a digital photographic system.

2.5 Scanning electron microscopy

The surface morphology of the untreated and the treated basalt fibers were observed by a JSM-5600LV Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) system. All

samples were gold coated prior to being loaded into the SEM chamber to induce conductivity and the SEM images were taken at magnifications of 500× and 5000×.

2.6 Wettability measurements

The surface wettability was determined by measuring the water contact angles on the fibers with an Optical Contact Angle Analyzer OCA15EC (Data Physics Instruments GmbH, Germany) based on the sessile drop technique. In order to magnify the mass change, five fibers were fixed parallel to each other on a measuring carrier. The fibers were straightened with certain tension. A small droplet of test liquid was placed on the fibers with a syringe and the test liquid was distilled water. A video camera recorded the process and the contact angle was calculated right after the water droplet landed on the fiber. The contact angle measurements were performed in an environment of 20 ° C and 65% RH. Fig.5. Shows the schematic diagram of the Dynamic Contact Angle Analyzer. The schematic diagram of dynamic contact angle analyzer is shown in Fig.7.

3. Result and discussion

3.1 Interfacial shear strength

The interfacial shear strength of basalt fibers to phenolic matrix is shown in Table 1. The IFSS are raised 41% when plasma treatment time are 30 and 40s, while 19% when plasma treatment time are 20s. As shown in Fig.5, it is easy to find that the mean

Fig.7. Schematic diagram of Dynamic Contact Angle Analyzer.

IFSS values of basalt fibers to phenolic matrix were significantly improved along with the increasing plasma treatment time. It demonstrates that the plasma treatment can improve the interfacial bonding between fiber and phenolic matrix. However, the mean IFSS values has no dramatic change between the sample treatment time from 30s to 40s. Previous study has found that when the treatment time changed from 30s to 40s, the interfacial shear strength always stays around 42 MPa. It indicated that increasing plasma treatment time could pose a negative influence on the etching effect for basalt fiber. The different results can be explained by that beside the APPJ system, other factors such as intermolecular forces, molecular structural stability also play important roles in determining plasma etching effectiveness. Like the tensile test, there must be a top IFSS point of the basalt/phenolic system. Of course, to ensure the stable embedding length is very necessary.

3.2 Single fiber tensile strength

The tensile strength of the untreated and the treated single basalt fibers is shown in Table 2. As shown in Fig.6, The tensile strength are raised 5.2% when plasma treatment time are 20s, while 3.6% when plasma treatment time are 40s. When plasma treatment time are 30s, the tensile strength are declined 1.2%. It is easy to find that no statistically significant difference among all groups, Not significant or important enough to be worth considering. It indicated that the plasma treatments had no detectable influence on the basalt fiber tensile strength. The tensile strength values of the plasma treated fibers often tended to be lower, which may be due to the introduction of cracks and pits on the fiber surface by plasma etching after long exposure to plasma.

3.3 Surface morphology

The surface morphology of the basalt fibers treated by plasma are exhibited in Fig. 4 with magnifications of 5000 × and 500 ×. The surface of untreated basalt fiber is relatively smooth. It was evident that

plasma treatment did etch the fiber surface to different extents for the three treated groups. As to Fig.2-B1,20s, no obvious change of basalt fiber surface morphology was found because of shortage of treatment time. Compared with Fig.2-B2,30s and Fig.2-B3,40s, distinct and dramatic varieties were observed. With the increase of treatment times, basalt fiber surfaces were varied from lubricity to roughness on account of surface defects, which were mainly lump-like and protuberance-like.

Taking the effect of Sizing materials on the surface of basalt fiber into consideration. Another group of basalt fibers was heated in the oven on the conditions of 100 degrees for four hours, to ensure that the Sizing materials on the surface has been removed. Then the samples were treated by plasma, and the SEM photographs were almost same to the unheated basalt fiber samples. The etching effect is not so obvious as the unheated basalt fiber samples, but the changes are not significant or important enough to be worth considering .

Fig.8. The Dynamic Contact Angle of the untreated basalt fiber

3.4 Wettability of fibers

The wettability of the fibers was determined by measuring the dynamic water contact angle is shown in Table 3. The static and dynamic contact angles are determined by the fiber morphology. The dynamic contact angle of the untreated basalt fiber is shown in Fig.8. It is found that, no significant difference was observed among the contact angles of untreated group and treated groups, which indicated the surface modification technique did not wreck the wettability of basalt fiber.

4. Conclusion

The geometrical and mechanical properties of basalt fibers have been investigated by scanning electron microscopy, tensile test and analysis. The plasma surface modification technique of basalt fibers can enhance the interfacial adhesion of fiber/phenolic system. However, treating basalt fibers with different plasma treatment times can result in different extents of improvement. When plasma treatment time is short, the fiber surface properties were improved obviously to favor interfacial adhesion with phenolic matrix . However, while plasma treatment time longer, the mean IFSS has no dramatic change. While the treated time grown from 30s to 40s. The interfacial shear strength always stays around 42 MPa. It was because the basalt fiber surfaces were varied from lubricity to roughness on account of surface defects, which were mainly lump-like and protuberance-like. During the plasma treatment, there were no significant difference of the single fiber tensile strength and the contact angles was found. The results indicate the plasma treatment has positive influence on the surface of basalt fibers in the improvement of adhesion property to phenolic resin matrix mainly through the physical etching effect. The Twenty-first Century saw a growing mood of cautious optimism within the composites community worldwide that fiber-reinforced composites will give rise to new composite material applications in a wide range of areas. Consequently, a wide rang of basalt

fiber-reinforced composites are under development/investigation or in production. To take the high temperature resistant property of phenolic resin into account, the basalt/phenolic composites is thus likely to provide major new area of opportunity for composite materials in the future.

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